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The LUNZ Hub's RESPECT Project

The interdisciplinary Rapid Engagement with Stressed Peatland Environments and Communities in Transformation (RESPECT) project is affiliated with the Land Use for Net Zero, Nature and People (LUNZ) Hub and is funded by the UKRI Land Use for Net Zero programme. RESPECT aims to produce data, methods, landholder tools and proposals for governance reforms to change agricultural practices on peatland. RESPECT brings together researchers across Scotland and England with expertise in the natural and social sciences, humanities and law. RESPECT will also produce the Peatland Triage Tool (PTT), providing decision-support for landowners, land managers, farmers and crofters (collectively 'landholders') seeking to undertake peatland restoration. Upon completion, RESPECT will be able to provide a solid evidence base, and tools to inform land use decisions in relation to the restoration and sustainable management of agricultural peatlands.

This response was drafted with input from across our interdisciplinary RESPECT Team.

RESPECT response to the Ecosystem Restoration Code survey

This document provides a response from the RESPECT project to the [Scottish Government's Ecosystem Restoration Code \(ERC\) survey](#). It raises fundamental questions about the desirability and purpose of developing a biodiversity trading scheme, citing evidence that the ecological effectiveness of voluntary markets is often limited and compliance markets only work if supported by effective implementation, governance and enforcement. Our response highlights concerns that a focus on natural capital trading risks conflict with Scottish public policy goals relating to land reform, community wealth building, new entrants and a just transition. RESPECT calls for a fundamental discussion on the purpose of another code, as well as robust regulation, and adequate public resourcing of independent monitoring, verification and enforcement.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Extra question: is the introduction of a biodiversity trading scheme a desirable development (incl. will it deliver on policy objectives and address the nature crisis)?

Before proceeding with the design and implementation of a new code for biodiversity trading, we believe that there must be a more fundamental public and policy discussion on whether it is a good idea to develop such a code in the first place. The engagement paper and survey assume consensus on biodiversity trading as a means to accelerate nature restoration through private investment, to support delivery of public policy objectives to halt the loss of nature by 2030 and to make significant progress to restoring nature by 2045. Yet, the efficacy and desirability of biodiversity markets is contested. We raise the following concerns:

The purpose of the Ecological Restoration Code is not clear:

The overarching purpose of the proposed Ecological Restoration Code remains unclear. Is the primary objective to incentivise and generate finance for active restoration, to prevent further degradation, or to provide a framework for offsetting unavoidable impacts? This foundational question must be resolved before any trading mechanism is developed. This also depends on how the Ecosystem Restoration Code aims to interact with other initiatives, for example, relating to planning, with us having received conflicting information on this point.

Well-designed compliance markets could, in theory, reduce environmental harm—especially in areas of high biodiversity value— by pushing developers to either not develop at all, or do all that they can to avoid,

minimise or restore biodiversity at every stage of development. Problems, however, arise when markets are used to leverage funds for conservation and restoration with limited checks and balances. The ecological effectiveness of biodiversity offset markets is contested, with many studies showing limited outcomes. This suggests that the challenges may not be solely technical or about market design but instead reflect deeper tensions in how biodiversity goals are framed—whether as "no net loss", net gain, or genuine ecological recovery.

Voluntary markets have delivered limited ecological outcomes:

Current evidence suggests that voluntary biodiversity trading schemes, even when regulated, have yielded limited ecological gains. Benabou provides the most recent and comprehensive review of the available data, indicating that outcomes are often inconsistent and may not achieve meaningful biodiversity uplift.¹

Compliance markets are only effective if supported by effective implementation, governance and enforcement:

The two most mature biodiversity markets – Wetland Mitigation Banking in the United States and the Biodiversity Offsets Scheme (BOS) (formerly BioBanking) in Australia – are compliance-based. In these schemes, companies are required to compensate for environmental impacts, creating a more direct and enforceable incentive to purchase credits and invest in conservation or restoration. This stands in contrast to voluntary schemes, where participation may be more sporadic and outcomes less predictable.

However, while there is evidence that linking biodiversity trading schemes to regulatory requirements—i.e., through compliance-based markets—can support market development by increasing the number of buyers and sellers,² the experience with Biodiversity Net Gain (BNG) in England highlights that market design alone is insufficient. Effective implementation, governance, and enforcement are essential for achieving real ecological outcomes. BNG has been subject to a number of criticisms, including:

- Limited measurable biodiversity gains resulting from weak monitoring and enforcement.³
- Significant administrative burdens placed on local planning authorities, which often lack the resources and expertise to oversee and regulate biodiversity compensation effectively.⁴
- Inadequate funding to support long-term governance, compliance checks, and site monitoring.⁵

Without dedicated funding and institutional capacity for robust monitoring, enforcement, and long-term oversight, biodiversity trading schemes will struggle to deliver genuine ecological, environmental, and social benefits—no matter how well-designed the market framework appears on paper.

Natural capital trading could undermine public policy goals:

The way existing (carbon) schemes operate in practice shows how natural capital trading undermines wider Scottish public policy objectives, such as, but not limited to, community wealth building (CWB) and land reform (including the Land Rights and Responsibilities Statement and Principle 6 of the Natural Capital Market Framework that investments support diverse and productive land ownership). Without sufficient support including adequate funding (see Q2 below) to ensure more equitable access to private finance, schemes may end up making large-scale landowners of the most degraded ecosystems richer, and speculation may lead to increased demand for scarce land resources with risks of further concentration of ownership.⁶ Questions of equity are, furthermore, not only relevant for national policies on land and communities. The Malawi Principles of the ecosystem approach under the Convention on Biological Diversity – cited by the paper as the basis for the proposed Ecosystem Restoration Code – have equity, local people and local knowledge at their core.

¹ S Benabou, 'Making Up for Lost Nature?: A Critical Review of the International Development of Voluntary Biodiversity Offsets' (2014) 5(1) Environment and Society [online].

² K Stephenson and B Tutko, 'The Role of in Lieu Fee Programs in Wetland/Stream Mitigation Credit Trading: Illustrations from Virginia and Georgia' (2018) 38(6) Wetlands 1211.

³ S O S E zu Ermgassen *et al*, 'Exploring the ecological outcomes of mandatory biodiversity net gain using evidence from early-adopter jurisdictions in England' (2021) 14(6) Conservation Letters [online].

⁴ E E Rampling *et al*, 'Achieving biodiversity net gain by addressing governance gaps underpinning ecological compensation policies' (2024) 38(2) Conservation Biology [online].

⁵ Ibid.

⁶ See subsequent reports from the Scottish Land Commission on rural land data, and insights from interviews with land agents, although natural capital-motivated purchases have slowed down in recent years.

Developing, governing and implementing a high integrity, functioning code with real ecological value requires regulation and, ultimately, public money. It needs to be considered at this stage whether this is the best use of public funds, or whether alternative public financing approaches are likely to be more effective and less risky.

SURVEY QUESTIONS

Question 1: What principles, actions or steps should be followed to ensure a high integrity ERC?

If the Scottish Government proceeds with development of a biodiversity market after having considered and addressed our concerns, we call for the establishment of a robust regulatory framework. Unregulated voluntary markets are not sufficient to ensure viable and high-integrity biodiversity trading. At the moment there is no specialised legislation and therefore natural capital investment, and trading are governed by existing environmental and property law. This leaves questions and potential gaps in relation to responsibilities, liabilities and enforcement. For example, consider the situation where a collaboration involves the setting up of a new company that carries liability for delivery of the project but is subsequently dissolved. What does this mean for responsibilities to deliver lasting ecological restoration as a public benefit? Current codes are showing a lack of high-level and coordinated thinking around delivery responsibilities.

Law can compel engagement with a biodiversity market through compliance obligations, but it must also hold market players to account, monitor and address potential negative environmental and social impacts. In addition, solid and inclusive governance structures are required to ensure that a high-integrity regulatory framework and principles, including those included in the Natural Capital Market Framework, are implemented.

A high-integrity ERC must ultimately seek genuine ecological restoration, not just move money around. There is a significant risk of simplifying biodiversity and local ecosystems to fit in with the world of finance which requires units/metrics that are easily replicable and tradable. Oversimplification of complex socio-ecological systems disregards context-specific human elements that are an integral part of ecosystems, and risks undermining conservation outcomes. Further, evidence shows that efforts to capture complexities by bundling different ecosystem services can lead to trade-offs, notably losses of ecosystem services on more high-value land as conservation activities seek to prioritise the least profitable land, despite an overall no net loss being recorded.⁷ Evidence also shows that different metrics produce vastly different landscape and species results,⁸ and may fail to protect non-target species or functions.⁹ In this regard, we also consider pluriversity scholarship that embraces alternative visions/worlds to repair our environment without replicating destructive forces and emphasising other ways of valuing nature, beyond its tradable components.¹⁰

Lastly, independent monitoring, verification, and enforcement must be adequately resourced and publicly funded. Relying on credit providers to undertake these functions themselves risks undermining ecological integrity, as the incentives for rigorous self-regulation in this context remain unproven.

Question 2: What actions and design features should the ERC adopt to enable land managers to participate in these markets?

To create an inclusive and equitable code, more thought needs to go into questions of project size. The proposed 200 hectares threshold effectively excludes 90% of Scottish landholdings from unilaterally engaging

⁷ M Drechsler, 'Bundling of Ecosystem Services in Conservation Offsets: Risks and How They Can Be Avoided' (2021) 10(6) Land 628.

⁸ J Kangas and M Ollikainen, 'Economic Insights in Ecological Compensations: Market Analysis With an Empirical Application to the Finnish Economy' (2019) 159 Ecological Economics 54; K H Simpson *et al*, 'Ecological and economic implications of alternative metrics in biodiversity offset markets' (2022) 36(5) Conservation Biology [online].

⁹ M Maron *et al*, 'Faustian bargains? Restoration realities in the context of biodiversity offset policies' (2012) 155 Biological Conservation 141; P R Armsworth *et al*, 'The cost of policy simplification in conservation incentive programs' (2012) 15(5) Ecology Letters 406; M Grimm, 'Metrics and Equivalence in Conservation Banking' (2021) 10(6) Land 565.

¹⁰ See M Blaser and M d I Cadena, 'Introduction: Pluriverse proposals for a world of many worlds' in Mario Blaser and Marisol de la Cadena (eds), *A World of Many Worlds* (Duke University Press 2018).

in a new biodiversity market (noting, however, that even within the other 10% decision-making power may still be shared, e.g., between landowners and tenants or crofters).

The proposals rely heavily on facilitation of collaborations and project aggregation, but experience with the carbon codes show that simple, large-scale projects are favoured by investors. How will a code address

transaction costs of collaborations that put small- and medium-sized landholders at a competitive disadvantage within a new biodiversity market? How will it build awareness and capacity across landholders and communities to engage and share benefits? Philanthropically funded, third-sector initiatives like Community Land Scotland's Natural Capital Community Partnerships are laudable. Yet, we believe that practical and financial support, including legal advice, support and up-front funding, should be embedded in the design and implementation of a code, if it was to be launched at all, to address unequal market access.

Question 3: How can the ERC be designed to ensure that it best meets the requirements of high-integrity investors and users of nature/biodiversity credits?

In addition to the points made above, it is necessary to align any metrics developed in the context of this potential code with other relevant initiatives, including in the context of planning and agricultural reform.

Question 4: How should the ERC support delivery of Scottish Government policy whilst being sufficiently accessible and attractive to market actors?

See above, there needs to be a much more fundamental discussion on the question *if* another code for private investment in natural capital is compatible with Scotland's public policy priorities, including, but not limited to:

- addressing the scale and concentration of land ownership
- the need to diversify land use
- community wealth building and community renewable energy
- attracting new entrants into farming
- protecting and restoring biodiversity
- creating a credible path to net zero
- supporting rural job retention and creation through the Just Transition.

And, if so, whether use of public resources to create and regulate a high-integrity and viable market for biodiversity credits is the most effective and efficient use of public funds to achieve these policy objectives.

The question should not be how we make a biodiversity trading scheme fit in with/contribute to the delivery of Scottish Government policy. The right questions are: what are our policy objectives, and what are the different options for delivering these policy objectives in an integrated way? Then, when considering all aspects of different options, including required resources, governance and decision-making power/control over natural resources and equitable considerations, is a biodiversity trading scheme the best tool in the box?